

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF STONES, SERUM IONS AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN UROLITHIASIS OF TIKRIT POPULATION, IRAQ

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ABSTRACT

Background: Area of high incidence of stone formation is recognized throughout the world, the etiological factors in this phenomenon are unknown. In general, stone formation is facilitated by factors that increase solutes concentration in the urine, alteration in pH, provides a nidus for precipitation, congenital abnormality, stasis, dehydration and altered Ca²⁺ metabolism and metabolic disorder by hyperparathyroidism, hyperuricemia and cystinuria oxalosis, hypercalcuria secondary o neoplasm or sarcoidosis vitamin D intoxication and abnormal renal function alter the urine composition such as renal tubular acidosis and foreign body. **Methodology:** A total of 135 patients with urolithiasis were studied including 91 males and 44 females. Patients aged between 15 to 70 years. and submitted for chemical analysis. 54 stones and some serum values like Serum Ca⁺², serum uric acid, serum P⁺⁵ and serum Mg⁺² among the patients were chemically analyzed. **Results:**

The majority among those mixed stones were composed of a mixture of calcium oxalate and calcium phosphate and uric acid with frequency almost 24%. Other stones were a mixture of calcium oxalate and calcium phosphate which were the second most common type of stones (22.2%). Serum Ca⁺², serum uric acid, serum P⁺⁵ and serum Mg⁺² among the patients were estimated. The serum values abnormalities included an increase in means of serum uric acid, serum calcium and serum phosphorous and their values were 0.37, 2.5 and 1.22 mmol/l respectively. **Conclusions:** Calcium-based stones predominate in males, while infection-

related stones (particularly ammonium magnesium phosphate) are more frequent in females. Calcium-based stones were primarily associated with elevated serum calcium, while infection-related stones (struvite) showed no significant biochemical elevation, supporting a non-metabolic etiology. The analysis demonstrates that urolithiasis is primarily associated with increased urinary pH and reduced serum magnesium levels, both of which create a favorable environment for crystal formation.

KEYWORDS: Urolithiasis, serum ions, ions values, age, gender.

INTRODUCTION

Most urinary calculi generally are composed primarily of a poorly soluble salt with a small amount of protein, containing calcium (Ca²⁺) as a main constituent.^[1,2] The direct cause of calculi is unknown and likely to be multifactorial, but urinary physiological abnormalities can be identified in more than 60% of patients.^[3,5] Hypercalciuria is the most common of these abnormalities, increases the risk of stone formation by raising saturation of stone forming salt and reducing the endogenous stone inhibitors.^[5,7] The prevalence of urolithiasis is approximately 2-3% of general population.^[8,9] The peak age of males is 30 years old, while in the women has bimodal age distribution with peaks at 35 and 55 years old. One kidney stone form the probability that a second stone will form within 5-7 years in approximately 50%^[4,10] Stone disease is 2-3 times more common in men than in women and it occurs more often in adults than in elderly and more often in elderly than in children. Urolithiasis occurs more frequently in hot dry areas than in temperate regions.^[11] Primary calculi are mainly of renal origin with underlying metabolic causes, while secondary stones develop around a foreign body in the urinary tract or as a result of chronic obstruction and infection. Anatomic anomalies and metabolic disorders are the most important etiological factors for childhood urolithiasis.^[12] Area of high incidence of stone formation is recognized throughout the world, the etiological factors in this phenomenon are unknown. In general, stone formation is facilitated by factors that increase solutes concentration in the urine, alteration in pH, provides a nidus for precipitation, congenital abnormality, stasis, dehydration and altered Ca²⁺ metabolism and metabolic disorder by hyperparathyroidism, hyperuricemia and cystinuria oxalosis, hypercalciuria secondary to neoplasm or sarcoidosis vitamin D intoxication and abnormal renal function alter the urine composition such as renal tubular acidosis and foreign body e.g. catheter.^[14,15,16]

Urinary Tract Infections (UTI's) are one of the most prevalent extra-intestinal bacterial infections. Nowadays, it represents one of the most common dis-eases encountered in medical practice affecting people of all ages from the neonate to the geriatric age group.^[17,18] Worldwide, about 150 million people are diagnosed with UTI each year.^[19] Most infections are caused by retro-grade ascent of bacteria from the faecal flora via the urethra to the bladder and kidney especially in the females who have a shorter and wider urethra and are more readily transferred by microorganisms.^[20] The structure of the females urethra and vagina makes it susceptible to trauma during sexual intercourse as well as bacteria being massaged up the urethra and into the bladder during pregnancy and/or child birth.^[21,22] Majority of UTI's are not life threatening and do not cause any irreversible damage. However, when the kidneys are involved, there is a risk of irreparable tissue damage with an increased risk of bacteremia.^[23,24,25,26,27]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of Specimens

This study was conducted in the Urology Department in Tikrit Teaching Hospital as a part of research programs for higher studies in College of Medicine, University of Tikrit. A total of 135 patients with urolithiasis were studied including 91 males and 44 females. Patients aged between 15 to 70 years. and submitted for chemical analysis.

Renal stone analysis

Calculi analysis testing was carried out according to methods carried out by other workers.^[15,28]

Serum ions and components estimation

The analysis of these serum ions and other components were done following Al-Jebouri and Hasen.^[29]

Statistical Analyses

Statistical analyses in the present study were done by using Microsoft Office Excel 2007, SPSS version 12(Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The programs used were F-test, T-test, least significant difference (LSD) and Chi-square.^[30]

RESULTS

The present study revealed that chemical composition of the 54 urinary stones was mostly mixed with frequency of 79.6%. The majority among those mixed stones were composed of a mixture of calcium oxalate and calcium phosphate and uric acid with frequency almost 24%. Other stones were a mixture of calcium oxalate and calcium phosphate which were the second most common type of stones (22.2%) but other stone types were rare with variable rates of frequency. Calcium oxalate and/ or phosphate stones account for most of the urinary stones obtained in the present study. There is a statistically significant association between renal stone composition and both gender and infection status (χ^2 test, $p < 0.05$). Calcium-based stones predominate in males, while infection-related stones (particularly ammonium magnesium phosphate) are more frequent in females. The moderate-to-strong Cramér’s V suggests a meaningful biological relationship rather than random variation(Figure 1).

Table 1. Distribution of renal stone chemical types among patients with underwent lithotomy or spontaneous shedding.

Infection	Type	Male		Female		Total	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Noninfectious	CaOx	4	4.4	1	1.9	5	9.3
	CaPO ₄	2	3.7	1	1.9	3	5.6
	CaPO ₄ Ox	10	18.5	2	3.7	12	27.2
	CaPO ₄ . +uric acid	2	3.7	1	1.9	3	5.6
	CaPO ₄ . +uric acid	2	3.7	1	1.9	3	5.6
	Uric acid	2	3.7	0	0	2	3.7
	Cystine	1	1.9	0	0	1	1.9
Infectious	AMP	1	1.9	4	7.4	5	9.3
	CaPO ₄ CO ₃	1	1.9	0	0	1	1.9
	CPO ₄ Ox.	3	5.6	2	3.7	5	9.3
	CaPO ₄ Ox. Uric acid. AMP	1	1.9	3	5.6	4	7.4
Total		36	66.7	18	33.3	54	100

AMP, ammonium magnesium phosphate.

Figure 1: Gender-based distribution of renal stone chemical composition among patients.

A comparison of some serum values like Serum Ca⁺², serum uric acid, serum P⁺⁵ and serum Mg⁺² among the patients was shown in Table 2. These serum values were distributed among patients who passed stones or underwent removal of their kidney stones and according to the chemical composition of the stones. One-way ANOVA demonstrated significant differences in serum calcium, magnesium, and uric acid levels across renal stone types (p < 0.05), whereas serum phosphate showed no significant variation. Post hoc Duncan analysis revealed that mixed calcium phosphate-oxalate-uric acid stones exhibited the highest levels of all measured ions, indicating a multifactorial metabolic origin. Calcium-based stones were primarily associated with elevated serum calcium, while infection-related stones (struvite) showed no significant biochemical elevation, supporting a non-metabolic etiology(Figure 2).

Table 2: The relationship between serum ion values and chemical nature of renal stones among patients.

Stone		Serum Uric acid		Serum calcium		Serum magnesium		Serum phosphate		Normal
Type	No.	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
CaOx	5	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	2
CaPO ₄	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
CaPO ₄ Ox	12	0	0	2	1	4	2	0	0	6
CaPO ₄ OxUA	13	3	1	3	2	3	3	1	0	4
CaPO ₄ UA	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Cystine	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Uric acid	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Struvite (AMP)	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
CaPO ₄ CO ₃	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
CaPO ₄ CO ₃ OxUA	5	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	3
CaPO ₄ OxUA (AMP)	4	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
Total of patients	54	8	2	6	3	10	7	2	2	27
Control	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19

N.B. Some patients have more than one metabolic abnormalities

Figure 2. Duncan Multiple Range Test of Serum Ion Levels Across Renal Stone Types.

The serum values abnormalities included an increase in means of serum uric acid, serum calcium and serum phosphorous and their values were 0.37, 2.5 and 1.22 mmol/l respectively. A decrease in the values was seen with serum magnesium with value equal to 0.75 mmol/l. The present study revealed the mean values of age, pH of the urine, serum values of Ca⁺², P⁺⁵, uric acid and Mg⁺² between patients and control groups (Table 3). The analysis demonstrates that urolithiasis is primarily associated with increased urinary pH and reduced serum magnesium levels, both of which create a favorable environment for crystal formation. While serum calcium and uric acid show mild elevation in patients, their contribution appears secondary. Age and phosphorus levels do not significantly differ between groups, indicating minimal influence on stone development. Linear regression analysis showing the relationship between mean serum parameters in patients and control groups. A strong positive correlation (R² = 0.999) indicates high consistency between the two groups across measured variables (Figure 3).

Table 3: Distribution of means of age, pH and some serum components of patients with urolithiasis.

Variable	Patients values(mmol/l)			Control values(mmol/l)		
	Male	Female	Average	Male	Female	Average
Age(Year)	35.83±14.7	36.33± 14.3	36.08±14.5	34.14±14	38.83±11.5	36.48±9.97
pH	5.65±1.11	6.86±1.12	6.25±1.1	4.97±0.4	5.58±0.5	5.27±0.49
Serum uric acid	0.41±0.05	0.33±0.05	0.37±0.05	0.35±0.04	0.29±0.05	0.32±0.05
Serum calcium	2.54±0.14	2.47±0.19	2.50±0.16	2.43±0.04	2.34±0.07	2.39±0.05
Serum phosphorus	1.25±0.35	1.19±0.34	1.22±0.35	1.15±0.17	1.22±0.16	1.18± 0.17
Serum magnesium	0.78±0.13	0.73±0.09	0.75±0.11	1.06±0.09	0.9±0.11	0.98±0.10

±, standard deviation; mmol/l, unit for serum values.

Figure 3. Dumbbell plot illustrating differences in mean serum parameters between patients and control groups.

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that the stones of mixed chemical composition were the most prevalent type with a frequency almost 80%. The majority of them were composed of calcium oxalate, calcium phosphate and uric acid which indicated a multiplicity of environmental factors. The second common stones were pure calcium oxalate, calcium phosphate, uric acid and cystine stones with frequencies of 9.3, 5.6, 3.7, and 1.9% respectively. There is a statistically significant association between renal stone composition and both gender and infection status (χ^2 test, $p < 0.05$). Calcium-based stones predominate in males, while infection-related stones (particularly ammonium magnesium phosphate) are more frequent in females. The moderate-to-strong Cramér's V suggests a meaningful biological relationship rather than random variation. However, among the different types of stones retrieved, the most common were calcium oxalate stones (64, 53.3%). This was followed by mixed calcium oxalate-phosphate stones found in 28 (23.3%) patients, uric acid stones in 16 (13.3%) patients, and struvite stones in eight (6.7%) patients. Cystine stones were the rarest and were found in four (3.3%) patients.^[23] Furthermore, Chemical analysis revealed that calcium oxalate was the most prevalent stone composition, identified in 61.2% of cases. Mixed-component stones were the second most common type, accounting for 23.1% of samples. Less frequently observed stone types included calcium phosphate (7.4%), struvite (4.1%), uric acid (3.3%), and cystine stones (0.8%). Overall, the results indicate that nephrolithiasis in this population predominantly affects males in the 30–50-year age group and is commonly associated with inadequate hydration, high dietary sodium intake, frequent tea consumption, and a prior personal history of kidney stones. Calcium-based stones, particularly calcium oxalate, were the dominant stone type identified in patients from Malakand Division.^[24] It was concluded elsewhere that . this cross-sectional study elucidates intricate curvilinear associations between dietary components and the risk of KS. We observed that the intake of citrus, melons, berries, tomatoes and milk was associated with a lower risk of KS. While our results advocate for a shift in preventive guidelines toward holistic dietary patterns, they must be interpreted with caution due to the limitations of the cross-sectional design. Future longitudinal studies are necessary to establish causality.^[27,31,32] A comparison of some serum values like Serum Ca^{+2} , serum uric acid, serum P^{+5} and serum Mg^{+2} among the patients was shown in Table 2. These serum values were distributed among patients who passed stones or underwent removal of their kidney stones and according to the chemical composition of the stones. One-way ANOVA demonstrated significant differences in serum calcium, magnesium, and uric acid levels across renal stone types ($p < 0.05$),

whereas serum phosphate showed no significant variation. Post hoc Duncan analysis revealed that mixed calcium phosphate-oxalate-uric acid stones exhibited the highest levels of all measured ions, indicating a multifactorial metabolic origin. The current study assessed stone composition and serum metabolic abnormalities in patients with recurrent renal calculi in our setting. Alam *et al.* findings indicated that calcium oxalate continues to be the most prominent type of stone.^[23] Recent meta-analyses state that calcium oxalate stones constitute 60% to 80% of all urinary stones, followed by the mixed calcium phosphate and uric acid stones.^[33,34] In our study, calcium oxalate stones constituted 53.3% of all cases, slightly less than the upper global range. These differences from the upper global range are likely due to differences in diet, water minerals, and the genetics of calcium and oxalate stones forming/calculating in urine.^[23] In addition, the relatively high number of mixed calcium oxalate-phosphate stones (23.3%) indicates that this population likely has overlapping metabolic disturbances, including vitamin D deficiency and mild hypercalcemia, which, in turn, likely facilitates phosphate to oxalate stones. The male predominance in our cohort is consistent with the well established differences in the epidemiology of stone disease that are attributed to men's higher urinary calcium and oxalate excretion as well as differences in diet and lifestyle.^[5,336]

The present study showed that serum values abnormalities included an increase in means of serum uric acid, serum calcium and serum phosphorous and their values were 0.37, 2.5 and 1.22 mmol/l respectively. A decrease in the values was seen with serum magnesium with value equal to 0.75 mmol/l. The present study revealed the mean values of age, pH of the urine, serum values of Ca^{+2} , P^{+5} , uric acid and Mg^{+2} between patients and control groups. Age and phosphorus levels do not significantly differ between groups, indicating minimal influence on stone development. Moreover, Kidney stone disease was most frequently observed among individuals aged 30–50 years, representing more than half of the study population (54.5%). Patients younger than 30 years constituted 27.3%, whereas those older than 50 years accounted for 18.2%. Regarding body mass index, most participants were classified as having a normal BMI (38.8%) or were overweight (36.4%), while 14.1% were obese and 10.7% were underweight.^[24,37,38] Furthermore, it was found by Alam *et al.* the average age was 42.6 ± 11.8 years (19-68 years), and the male-to-female ratio was 2.3:1. The average BMI was 26.4 ± 3.8 kg/m², and 38.3% were classified as overweight or obese. A family history of urolithiasis was documented in 29.1% of the study population, while 32.5% reported inadequate daily fluid intake (<2 L/day)^[23,39,40,41,42,43] It was found that urolithiasis

was demonstrated when solutes crystallize out of urine to form stones. Kidney stone may occur due to various factors like anatomic abnormality leading to urinary stasis, low urine volume, dietary factors with high oxalate or high sodium, urinary tract infections, systemic acidosis, medications and due to inheritable genetic reasons such as cystinuria.^[44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51]

CONCLUSIONS

Calcium-based stones predominate in males, while infection-related stones (particularly ammonium magnesium phosphate) are more frequent in females. Calcium-based stones were primarily associated with elevated serum calcium, while infection-related stones (struvite) showed no significant biochemical elevation, supporting a non-metabolic etiology. The analysis demonstrates that urolithiasis is primarily associated with increased urinary pH and reduced serum magnesium levels, both of which create a favorable environment for crystal formation. Age and phosphorus levels do not significantly differ between groups, indicating minimal influence on stone development. Linear regression analysis showing the relationship between mean serum parameters in patients and control groups.

Statement of Ethics

All the procedures involving human participation were conducted in strict accordance with ethical standards of Institutional Research Committee, Department of Scientific Research, Tikrit University as well as the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments or equivalent ethical norms.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise.

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